

ALL-Ready Project Deliverable 7.3

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

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Policy report

Policy briefs on cross-cutting themes at the project level

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Disclaimer

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List of abbreviations

AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (principles)
Partnership AGROECOLOGY	Horizon Europe Partnership "Accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures"
WP	Work package

1. Introduction

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Union (EU)'s Research Executive Agency with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs and Research Infrastructures that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project has contributed to addressing the multiple challenges that farming systems are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

1.1 Purpose of the Deliverable

This deliverable summarises the cross-cutting outcomes of ALL-Ready and presents recommendations for policy-makers, funders, communities of living labs, and research infrastructures using the format of policy briefs.

1.2 Policy briefs: Purpose and process of development

The purpose of the policy briefs is to disseminate key lessons and policy recommendations (including research policies and funding programmes) to harness the potential of a European Network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures for accelerating transitions to agroecology.

In line with the Communication and Dissemination Plan (Haller *et al.*, 2021; D7.1), following target audiences were identified: policy-makers and funding organisations at European, national, regional and local levels. ALL-Ready has created two types of policy briefs:

- **Policy briefs covering specific themes:** they contain key learnings and policy recommendations from the ALL-Ready work packages (WP). These briefs were developed by a team coordinated under WP4 Implementation and sustainability of the network. These policy briefs are reported in D4.4 *Policy briefs for regional, national and EU-level policy makers*.
- **Policy briefs covering cross-cutting issues at project level:** These briefs were developed by a team coordinated under WP7 Communication and dissemination and are reported in this deliverable.

Under WP7, the following topics were selected for policy briefs: overview of Living Lab Networks in Agriculture, their success factors and policy implications (McPhee *et al.*, 2023), Co-creation experiences of the ALL-Ready Pilot Network (Varga *et al.*, 2023) and finally a summary of the key messages of the ALL-Ready final conference (McKhann *et al.*, 2023).

2. Overview of policy briefs

The messages of the policy briefs are summarised in Table 1 and listed together with their respective links in the Zenodo repository. The full versions of the policy briefs can be found in Annex 1.

Table 1 Overview of policy briefs and repository links.

Title	Link to Zenodo repository
<p>Policy Brief: Living Lab Networks in Agriculture: Success Factors and Policy Implications</p> <p>The Policy Brief emphasises the significance of consolidation processes for the long-term success of the diverse European Network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures. These processes include building trust in relationships, establishing, reviewing, and adapting network governance, and evolving network infrastructure. Furthermore, funding programs should promote research into defining network types and their characteristics, as they significantly impact network functionality and the support required from both policy and practice.</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042097</p>
<p>Policy Brief: Co-creation experiences of the ALL-Ready Pilot Network</p> <p>Co-creation is a widely embraced concept in various domains, but its practical implementation poses challenges for policymakers. The ALL-Ready project has actively tested co-creation methods within its pilot network, comprising agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures. This policy brief succinctly outlines the key results of these co-creation experiences and offers policy recommendations for future policymaking considerations.</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042101</p>
<p>Policy Brief: Key messages of the ALL-Ready final conference</p> <p>To advance agroecology, sustained long-term political and financial investments are essential at various governance levels, including local, regional, national, and European. A holistic approach is needed to deepen our comprehension of the advantages and obstacles in transitioning to agroecology. This approach encourages innovation through collaborative initiatives aimed at mitigating and distributing the risks linked to the transition. Ensuring a continuous dialogue between policymakers and stakeholders is vital to facilitate the transition effectively.</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/10063976</p>

3. Key findings and policy recommendations

The key findings and policy recommendations highlighted in the three policy briefs are summarised below:

- The **main benefits of a European Network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures** are:
 - Strengthened networking and collaboration, enhanced portfolios of research and innovation activities;
 - Exchange and diffusion of knowledge resulting in further improvements in the governance of agroecology living labs and research infrastructures;
 - Promotion of value chain solutions for accelerating transitions to agroecology;
 - Need of research policies and funding requirements to accommodate an adaptive governance, roles and responsibilities of different types of actors and dynamic action plans of the network;
 - Close collaboration with other networks in agriculture and rural development will enhance synergies in increasing knowledge about research and innovation for agroecology transitions.
- **Co-creation** - in a living lab setting - is a powerful approach of open innovation, where the development of new value happens in cooperation with experts and a variety of stakeholders from industry, public institutions, and civil society, and in which the needs of the user play a central role.
 - Successful co-creation requires a shared purpose and sufficient capacity among participants. Connections within networks should be strengthened. Specific policies (operational and financial) and evaluation processes need to be developed.
- **Systems Thinking** is an indispensable competency for actors engaged in Agroecology Transition. It enables a profound understanding of the underlying issues and consequences associated with context-specific agroecological innovations, effectively supporting their development and implementation.
 - Training on systems thinking is essential for agroecology initiatives. Tailored trainings are needed for practitioners, policymakers, funders as well as scientists.
 - Policy interventions aimed at strengthening the skills and competencies of actors in agroecology initiatives should include provisions for systems thinking training.
- **Agricultural knowledge and innovation systems** (AKIS) are central to supporting living labs.
 - However, the capacities of AKIS across Europe to support the development of living labs vary considerably. Different approaches are needed to strengthen the capacity of AKIS, and should focus on geographical 'hotspots' where AKIS are particularly weak.
 - The heterogeneous nature of the European Network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures amplifies the importance of consolidation processes for long-term success, including building trust, governance, and infrastructure.
- Funding programs should encourage research into defining **network types and their characteristics**, as these have implications for network function and support by policy.
- The ALL-Ready project emphasises the importance of **rigorous data management guidelines** that are compliant with the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) principles and ethics.
 - Ethical and replicable data management procedures, specialised data management teams and developing FAIR-compliant collaborative repositories are essential to maximise the impact of research and advance faster towards sustainable agriculture in Europe.

- The ALL-Ready project provides a detailed framework for agroecology data management.
- **Engaging policy-makers and stakeholders** in a consistent dialogue is indispensable to facilitate the transition towards agroecology.
 - **Long-term political and financial investments** are vital at local, regional, national, and European level to foster research that provides evidence on the effectiveness of agroecology in different dimensions. A comprehensive approach is required to enhance our understanding of the benefits and challenges of transitioning to agroecology. This involves fostering innovation through collaborative efforts aimed at minimising and sharing the risks associated with the transition.

The **adoption of open innovation methodologies**, such as living labs and research infrastructures, which encourage co-creation in real-life settings with the active participation of all relevant stakeholders, is key to achieving long-term impact. Those will be at the core of the Horizon Europe Partnership “Accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures” (Partnership AGROECOLOGY) to be launched in early 2024 under Horizon Europe.

4. Dissemination of policy briefs

The policy briefs have been published through project and other channels (e.g. ALL-Ready website, newsletter, social media, [Zenodo](#)). This included the communication channels as well as professional networks of project partners, and the network of the consortium of the Partnership AGROECOLOGY.

- Project website – News Item [The ALL-Ready Policy Briefs have been published](#)
- Final ALL-Ready project newsletter
- Project social media channels
 - Facebook: [We are gladly announcing that the policy briefs... | Facebook](#)
 - X/Twitter: [ALL-Ready on X: "We are gladly announcing that the policy briefs produced during the ALL-Ready project are now publicly available"](#)
 - LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7129759963773579264>

5. Acknowledgements

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Annex 1 - Policy briefs

Policy brief

Living Lab Networks in Agriculture: Success Factors and Policy Implications

Chris McPhee and Gerald Schwarz

Key messages

The heterogeneous nature of the European Network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures amplifies the importance of allowing for consolidation processes as a key factor for long-term success. Important consolidation processes include the building of trust in relationships to enable open exchange, the establishment, review and adaptation of network governance, and the evolution of network infrastructure.

Funding programmes need to encourage research into defining network types and their characteristics as these have implications for how a network functions and how it may need to be supported by both policy and practice.

AAFC's nationwide network of living labs and the future European Network. Source: AAFC and ALL-Ready project.

Introduction

Over the last 5 years, the agriculture sector worldwide has seen increasing attention being paid to the application of the living labs approach to innovation management due to its potential for addressing urgent environmental, economic, and social challenges. Policy makers and practitioners are attracted to the living labs approach because it holds great promise for

accelerating the co-development and adoption of innovations, for enabling transitions towards more resilient and sustainable agricultural systems, for fostering increased scientific collaboration and knowledge exchange, and for strengthening the link between long-term policy objectives and the practical challenges faced by farmers on a daily basis.

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Living Lab Networks in Agriculture: Success Factors and Policy Implications – September 2023

The living labs approach to innovation management is now generally well established and is supported by a large body of scholarly literature (e.g., see reviews by Hossain et al., Greve et al., 2021, Hossain et al., 2019; Westerlund et al., 2018) and ample practical cases describing the implementation of individual living labs. However, new challenges are emerging through the recent trend towards large-scale networks of living labs. This is particularly evident in the agriculture sector.

Living Lab Networks

An individual living lab can be seen as a type of small-scale network necessary for open innovation processes, and it therefore functions as a local innovation ecosystem (Leminen et al., 2012). However, this policy brief focuses on broader networks that link together living labs and other organizations at regional, national, or international scales. Such networks may also function as “networks of networks” that enable sharing not only between living labs and other organizations (e.g., research infrastructures) but also between networks and can therefore play a key role in system-wide transitions, as expected in the case of agroecology (Mambrini-Doudet et al., 2022). Examples include the [Canada Agroecosystem Living Labs Network \(CALL-Net\)](#), the French network of living labs under the [Territoires d’innovation](#) scheme, the [European Network of Living Labs \(ENoLL\)](#) subnetwork of agriculture and agri-food living labs, the [Long-Term Agroecosystem Research Network \(LTAR\)](#) in the United States, the proposed set of soil health living labs under the [Soil Mission](#) and the future European Network of agroecology living labs and research infrastructures as part of the [Horizon Europe Partnership on Agroecology](#), which is the focus of the [ALL-Ready](#) project.

Such networks are becoming increasingly common, but they may not share common characteristics, largely owing to differences in how they are created. Accordingly, this policy brief synthesizes experiences from the Canadian Agroecosystem Living Lab Network and the assessment of key factors for the future European Network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures. As these contrasting experiences show, certain network characteristics have implications for how a

network functions and how it may need to be supported by both policy and practice.

Experiences from Canada and Europe

Since 2018, Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada (AAFC) has been building a nationwide network of 13 agroecosystem living labs to accelerate the development and adoption of farming practices to address urgent agri-environmental issues, especially climate change. This network comprises more than 1000 participants, whose work is supported at the network level by a dedicated team at AAFC that provides coordination in addition to supporting knowledge exchange, innovation support, capacity building, data sharing, scientific integration, and scaling of solutions.

Through policy development and program implementation since 2018, the network in Canada has been built up “from scratch” in a series of phases. Each living lab is unique and responds to local, place-based challenges and production systems, but across the nationwide network, all of the living labs share a common implementation model, funding source and timelines, and ultimate objectives (e.g., increasing carbon sequestration, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and providing other environmental co-benefits).

In contrast, the proposed European network of living labs and research infrastructures follows an “assembled” model of network creation, whereby existing or new components are gathered together into a unified but heterogeneous network. Among its component organizations, such a network may display much greater diversity of objectives, funding sources and timelines, and implementation models. We do not argue that one model is better than another, but the differences in the resulting homogeneity or heterogeneity do suggest some advantages and disadvantages in terms of diversity, comparability, coordination, etc.

Regardless, similar to the situation in Canada, the expected benefits of the European network include strengthened networking and collaboration, supporting long-term funding

strategies, continuity and enhanced portfolios of research and innovation activities, and strengthened knowledge creation, exchange and diffusion (Schwarz et al., 2022; McPhee et al., 2021). Examples of mechanisms to deliver these benefits include:

- i) the provision of tools and databases supporting long-term and transboundary data collection and management of interdisciplinary experiments
- ii) thematic working groups or sub-networks
- iii) methodological guidance on, and coordination of, collaboration (e.g. in fundraising, and addressing operational challenges)
- iv) establishment of close linkages to national level networks to ensure good information flow and a wider reach of actors on the ground.

Key lessons learnt

The heterogeneous nature of the assembled European Network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures needs to be reflected in its implementation and management and has implications for the supporting policy and funding environment.

The European Network will include a diverse range of living labs and research infrastructures with experiences differing in terms of thematic expertise and the level of expertise in running an initiative. Enabling adaptive governance that responds to changes in size and experiences of its members will utilise the benefits from, and values of, the diversity of its composition. The heterogeneous nature of the network requires the allocation of adequate resources for network management and coordination.

Allowing for consolidation processes and activities is a key factor of success for the long-term implementation of a heterogeneous network. Time is needed to develop relationships enabling trusted open exchange, to establish, review and adapt governance processes, as well as objectives, values and activities of the network, and to develop and evolve network infrastructure.

Generating evidence on the benefits of developing and participating in the European Network fosters buy-in and commitment from funding organisations and living labs and research infrastructures. This requires the development of tools or approaches to monitor and evaluate the performance of the network in a transparent and sound manner.

A further key factor in facilitating knowledge exchange, data sharing and integration of scientific methods and results between living labs and research infrastructures is the development of guidelines and protocols to support data harmonization and mobilisation.

Allowing for consolidation processes and activities is a key factor of success for the long-term implementation of a heterogeneous network.

Policy recommendations

- recognize in research and funding policies the long-term nature of network implementation and continuity that go beyond standard R&I project cycles.
- ensure eligibility of management and coordination activities of the different types of actors engaged in the Network and ring-fence funding for these kinds of activities in funding programmes.
- require in research and funding policies the generation of sound evidence of the performance and impact of the European Network through transparent monitoring and evaluation of its processes and activities.
- ensure common application of EU standards and requirements for data management and protection that facilitate transboundary data harmonization and mobilization
- encourage research into defining network types and their characteristics and develop tools and approaches to increase network coordination and performance

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Policy brief

Co-creation experiences of the ALL-Ready Pilot Network

Korinna Varga and Valéria Csonka

Summary

Co-creation has become a popular concept across different fields and sectors. However, the implementation in practice is less straightforward for policy makers. In the ALL-Ready project, co-creation methods have been applied and tested through different activities in the project's pilot network involving agroecology Living Labs (LLs) and Research Infrastructures (RIs) established by the project. This policy brief aims to summarise the major outcomes of the co-creation experiences and provides policy recommendations based on these, providing to serve as recommendations for future policy considerations.

Introduction

Co-creation - in a living lab setting - is a living concept and refers to a form of open innovation, where the development of new value happens in cooperation among the experts and a variety of stakeholders from industry, research, public institutions, and civil society, in which the needs of the user play a central role.

Co-creation in Living Labs (LLs) supports the transition towards agroecology and the co-development of knowledge through tacit and implicit knowledge sharing. Furthermore, it is particularly important to involve the knowledge of local communities and to foster the participation of all actors involved in agroecology from the local to the global level (from farmers to

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 Policy Brief - Accelerating agroecology transition using living labs: policy enablers and barriers – September 2023

consumers). This can mobilise and bring together complementary and transversal agroecological expertise which increases the speed and uptake of innovations.

Research Infrastructures (RIs) on the other hand provide services for the research community in the first place. Although co-creation is not a requirement, there are Research Infrastructures that support the agroecology transition through co-design and co-development of research environments. Moreover, stakeholders such as farmers and advisors are becoming more and more involved in systemic experiments, (e.g. redesign of farm systems or long-term monitoring), thereby creating space for open innovation and co-creation processes similar to Living Labs. The ALL-Ready project applied the concept of co-creation through its pilot network which acted as a testbed to not only experiment with the different concepts but also to co-create and co-design new tools and activities for the pilot members and for the larger agroecology community.

Approach and results

Co-creation activities applied a range of methods and mixtures of methods tailored to the goals of each event. These events led to recommendations for the future European Network of Agroecology LLs and RIs, and to the design of a Capacity Building Programme and a Virtual Research Environment for the agroecology community.

The following co-creation methods were used :

- **Validation sessions:** participants discussed a predefined set of topics and ideas to spark debate and arrive at a common understanding or set of preferences. Based on this, tasks or actions were prioritised.

- **Mapping:** this method involves collecting information orally or in written on a given area of interest, and then recording it on an online workboard in which the group can provide feedback.
- **Match-making:** this method helped to identify and connect members with common agroecological interests.
- **Peer assist:** during these sessions 1-2 peer members were invited to provide their experience, insights and knowledge on a commonly identified problem.
- **Carousel brainstorming:** provided space for small groups to get acquainted with new information or review existing information through movement, conversation, and reflection.
- **Two-step evaluation:** feedback, satisfaction and opinions were evaluated through short questionnaires after each meeting, individual and feedback calls. At the end of the project, members filled in a longer survey and participated in a group reflection on experiences about the whole co-creation process.

Results

The 18-month long co-creation process of the pilot network,, has enabled the efficient collection and validation of information and created space for ideation. Co-creation gave the members a sense of ownership and decision-making power over the activities which increased their participation. The iterative nature of the process helped members to evaluate their current LL / RI practices or ways of

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thinking. Finally, the co-creation methods facilitated networking, which at its turn nurtures long-term collaboration.

One of the main lessons learned is that fun and interactive methods should be integrated in the co-creation process, otherwise workshops risk becoming “dry” or boring. Furthermore, resorting to online workshops only reduces the potential for co-creation and gathering quality inputs. Face-to-face meetings greatly improve the effectiveness of co-creation by providing a more open and personal environment for discussion and stimulating greater involvement in the exercises.

“Co-creation contributes to a shift from practice-based to system thinking.”

*Statement from a pilot network member

Conclusions

The experiences in the ALL-Ready project showed that the involvement of all members in these processes facilitated learning from shared expertise which again further inspired members to experiment, adopt different LL / RI practices or to assess their practices from a different perspective. The co-creation enhanced the sense of ownership and facilitated decision-making. The combination of co-creation methods used in the workshops supported networking, which stimulated long-term collaboration. Finally, monitoring and evaluation of the whole co-creation process is essential and needs to be planned from the beginning to improve future co-creation processes.

Implications and policy recommendations

Purpose of co-creation

Always develop and maintain a shared vision and purpose among different stakeholders in the co-creation process, besides trying to find a solution to a specific problem. In the pilot network, the shared goal of pursuing a transition towards agroecology was a significant motivation for the members to get engaged in the process.

Diverse networks should be strengthened to accelerate innovation

Agroecology LLs and RIs in the pilot network are local or national networks themselves. The network functioned successfully because strong linkages between different sectors, research institutes and perspectives were formed. Such connections are essential for ensuring that new ideas are quickly turned into tangible solutions, thereby facilitating rapid innovations.

Build capacities for co-creation

Successful co-creation requires careful planning, trust-building, and continuous communication to meet the needs of all stakeholders. Therefore, working with experts in co-creation and allocating appropriate resources is necessary.

Develop policies to enable efficient co-creation

Build an adequate operational and financial environment to accelerate co-creation. Also, integrate the co-creation approach into policy-making processes (especially in relation to agriculture) to increase ownership and a sense of contribution to long-term policy decisions.

Evaluation of the co-creation process is a must

An adaptive monitoring and evaluation framework should be put in place at the beginning of the whole co-creation process involving all stakeholders to ensure that conclusions are drawn and required changes are identified.

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Further reading

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Varga, K. and Fehér, J. (2022) Second report of ALL-Ready pilot co-creation experiences

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Policy brief

How Living Labs and Research Infrastructures can support the Agroecology Transition in Europe – Key messages of the final conference

Key messages

- Long-term political and financial investments are vital at local, regional, national, and European level to foster research that provides evidence on the effectiveness of agroecology in different dimensions.
- A comprehensive approach is required to enhance our understanding of the benefits and challenges of transitioning to agroecology. This involves fostering innovation through collaborative efforts aimed at minimizing and sharing the risks associated with the transition.
- The adoption of open innovation methodologies, such as living labs and research infrastructures, which encourage co-creation in real-life settings with the active participation of all relevant stakeholders, is key to achieving long term impact.
- The European Partnership on Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures, launching in early 2024 under Horizon Europe aims to accelerate the agroecology transition across Europe by supporting a network of living labs and research infrastructures.
- Engaging policy-makers and stakeholders in a consistent dialogue is indispensable to facilitate the transition.

Source: FiBL, Lisa Haller

Source: FiBL, Lisa Haller

ALL-Ready - The European Agroecology Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase
 Policy Brief - The benefits of a European Network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures –September 2023

Challenges and policy context

Today, our agricultural and food systems are facing multiple challenges, such as climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality. Agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems and thus contribute to addressing these challenges.

The pivotal role of agroecology in supporting key European policies, such as the Green Deal, is widely recognised by the European Institutions.

However, for agroecology transition we need a real change of paradigm in science as well as in practices for a large number of farmers in Europe.

We need strong incentives to create policies and regulations that are coherent and support sustainable and resilient agri-food systems – in terms of legislation, funding and other types of support, at the local, regional, national and European levels, including the Common Agricultural Policy.

Conclusions

We urgently need resilient and sustainable agri-food systems. The ALL-Ready and AE4EU (Agroecology for Europe, the sister CSA project of ALL-Ready) projects have taken the initial steps towards facilitating this essential transition. The increasing prominence of Agroecology on the political agenda is an important step in achieving the Green Deal and in particular the Farm to Fork and Biodiversity strategies. The adoption of open innovation methodologies, such as living labs, which encourage co-creation in real-life settings with the active participation of all relevant stakeholders, is key to achieving long term impact.

Policy recommendations

- Increased funding is needed for research in agroecology ([Committee of the Regions \(CDR\) agroecology report](#)), this will provide evidence on the effectiveness of agroecology in different dimensions.
- Long-term investment is vital, while the upcoming future European partnership on agroecology with its 7-10 year time-frame is an excellent step, undoubtedly it will only be start. Long term political and financial investments are needed at local, regional, national and European levels.
- Eco-schemes are a promising tool and some of them promote agroecological practices. However, a more progressive approach is required, — one that goes beyond mere conditionality.
- A comprehensive approach is needed, that enhances the understanding of the benefits and challenges of an agroecology transition. This involves fostering innovation through collaborative efforts aimed at minimizing and sharing the risks associated with the transition.
- We need an improved accessibility and dissemination of knowledge related to agroecology, reinforcing the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS). To ensure progress, a robust framework and monitoring of data must be established.
- A consistent engagement and dialogue with policy-makers and stakeholders is indispensable to facilitate agroecology transition.

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Further information

Press release of the conference: <https://www.all-ready-project.eu/communication/news-events/news/how-living-labs-and-research-infrastructures-can-support-the-agroecology-transition-in-europe-insights-from-two-european-projects-all-ready-and-ae4eu.html>

Recordings of the conference: <https://www.all-ready-project.eu/communication/news-events/news/recordings-of-the-final-conference.html>

Committee of the Regions (CDR) agroecology report: <https://cor.europa.eu/en/our-work/Pages/OpinionTimeline.aspx?opId=CDR-3137-2020>

European Partnership: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/agriculture-forestry-and-rural-areas/ecological-approaches-and-organic-farming/partnership-agroecology_en
<https://www.ae4eu.eu/>

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About ALL-Ready: ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs (LL) and Research Infrastructures (IR) that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

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